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Research Article

**UNCHARACTERISTIC RANGE OF FUNDUS FLUORESCEIN
ANGIOGRAPHY CHARACTER IN MIDDLE SEROUS
CHORIORETINOPATHY**¹Dr Muhammad Waleed Khalid, ²Dr Zaema Kanwal, ³Dr Sundas Asghar¹Punjab Medical College Faisalabad²Ameer ud Din Medical College, Lahore³University Medical and Dental College Faisalabad**Article Received:** April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

Background: An eye illness that originates visual mutilation, frequently temporarily, typically in single eye called central serous chorioretinopathy. A indistinct or dreary mark in the middle illustration field is frequent when the retina is disconnected. Fundus Fluorescein Angiography can reveal abnormal blood vessels or damage to the lining underneath the retina.

Objective: This study aimed at determination of atypical and unusual patterns of this disease on Fundus Fluorescein Angiography (FFA).

Design of study: This study was descriptive.

Patients & Methods: All those patients who were diagnosed with central serous chorioretinopathy and undergone FFA, were selected for study. Atypical patterns of this disease were analyzed. When no proper result was found with FFA, optical coherence tomography was done in order to get the proper conclusions.

Results: There were 23 patients included in this study. Abnormal FFA features were shown in 12 patients. These features were: various ink spots in one eye and both eyes, pigment epithelial detachment along with CSR but demonstration of pigment epithelial detachment only on FFA, growth of blood vessels originating from choroid along with CSR where these vessels demonstrate on FFA only and no leakage from CSR is shown on FFA, smoke stalk and ink spot in same eye.

Conclusion: Diagnostic problems can arise due to abnormal features of CSR. These features must be analyzed carefully by the doctors. Such cases should be treated by keeping in view, their association with eye diseases.

Key words: FFA, OCT Atypical CSR.

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INTRODUCTION:

Central serous retinopathy (CSR) is the illness of eye that originates the visual mutilation, frequently impermanent, typically in single eye [1, 2, 3]. While the turmoil is vigorous, it is differentiated by seepage of solution below the retina that has a tendency to mount up beneath the middle macula. These consequences in distorted or indistinct hallucination [4, 5]. A distorted or gray blemish in the middle illustration field is frequent when the retina is disconnected. Condensed visual perception may continue following the liquid has departed. In CSR, two regular characters of seepage are smoke trail and inkspot manifestation in FFA [6, 7]. Irregular characters may contain bilateral and a variety of foci and deprived prediction. CSR has various diseases associated with it which include Cushing's syndrome, pregnancy, increased corticosteroid levels in body, a type personality etc. Various eye diseases are also related with it such as optic disc pit, bullous retinal detachment which might expand in relationship with the exercise of universal steroids and CNV. Recurrence is seen in 45% cases of CSR. Such factors may change the normal patterns of FFA. This study aimed at

determination of atypical and unusual patterns of this disease on FFA [8].

PATIENTS & METHODS:

This study was done at Ophthalmology department, Amanat Eye Hospital in Rawalpindi and Sheikh Zayed Medical College and Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan. Study duration was one year. All those patients who were diagnosed with CSR and undergone FFA, were selected for study. Atypical patterns of this disease were analyzed. When no proper result was found with FFA, optical coherence tomography was done in order to get the proper conclusions. Detailed history was also taken from these patients. The collected data was analyzed using 15th version of SPSS.

RESULTS:

There were 23 patients added in this learning. Average age of patients was 36+_{5.1} years. Among patients, male were 16. Normal features including single smoke stalk and single inkspot (in one eye) was shown in 11 cases. In 5 patients, there was presence of single smoke stalk whereas, single inkspot in 6 patients. In 12 patients, abnormal features were present which included 8 males.

Table I: Frequency of different presentations (N = 23)

Presentation	Subtypes	No (%)	
Typical (48%)	11	Single inkblot in one eye	6 (26%)
		Single smoke stalk in one eye	5 (22%)
Atypical (52%)	12	Inkblot and smoke stalk (same eye)	2 (8.6%)
		Multiple inkblots (same eye)	4 (17.3%)
		Multiple inkblots (both eyes)	3 (13%)
		CSR with PED	1 (4.3%)
		CSR with CNV	1 (4.3%)
		CSR with no leakage	1 (4.3%)

DISCUSSION:

Total number of selected cases was 23 out of which 30% were women and men were 70%. Patients demonstrating typical CSR showed mean age of 36 years. Patients demonstrating atypical features came up with the mean age of 38 years. Inks spots were shown more in number in typical features of CSR. This finding is same with that of Imtiaz et al and a finding came out from Srinagar. In this study, there were more patients demonstrated with anomalous characteristics of CSR on FFA [8, 9, 10]. Abnormal FFA features were: various ink spots in one eye and both eyes, pigment epithelial detachment alongwith CSR but demonstration of pigment epithelial detachment only on FFA, growth of blood vessels originating from choroid alongwith CSR where these vessels demonstrate on FFA only and no leakage from CSR is shown on FFA, smoke stalk and ink spot in same eye.

Two cases were seen with smoke stalk and ink spot markings in the same eye. Abnormal features may have link with various disorders and many studies have proved this point. Some reports demonstrated the link of multifocal CSR with TB [11-12]. When CSR is vigorous, it is differentiated by seepage of liquid beneath the retina that has a tendency to mount up beneath the middle macula. These consequences in indistinct or unclear vision. Condensed visual perception might continue following the liquid has gone.

Various eye diseases are also related with it such as optic disc pit, bullous retinal detachment which might expand in connection by the exploit of universal steroids and CNV [13]. Recurrence is seen in 45% cases of CSR. Such factors may change the normal design of FFA. In this study, when no proper result was found with FFA, optical coherence tomography (OCT) was done in order to get the proper conclusions. However, this study aimed at determination of anomalous and unusual patterns of CSR on FFA.

CONCLUSION:

Various diagnostic problems can arise due to anomalous designs of CSR. These designs must be analyzed carefully by the doctors. Such cases should be treated by keeping in view, their association with eye diseases.

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